

IMPROVING THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGY IN REGULATING AND IMPLEMENTING THE MARKETING ACTIVITIES OF REGIONAL TRADE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article examines the issues of enhancing the role of marketing strategy in regulating and implementing the marketing activities of regional trade enterprises.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы регулирования маркетинговой деятельности региональных торговых предприятий и повышения роли маркетинговой стратегии в её реализации.

Key words. Trade, trading enterprise, marketing, marketing strategy, region, regulation.

Ключевые слова. Торговля, торговое предприятие, маркетинг, маркетинговая стратегия, регион, регулирование.

For the activities of regional trade enterprises to be effective under competitive market conditions, marketing plays a crucial role. Marketing reflects the process of identifying customer needs, positioning products or services in the market, and implementing advertising and sales strategies. Taking into account the rapid changes, multifaceted nature, and complexity of modern business, a marketing strategy demonstrates the firm's importance in achieving and maintaining a competitive position by ensuring efficient use of resources and meeting market demand. At the corporate level, this can be represented through three main groups aimed at satisfying market needs. [1]. For regional enterprises, the main objectives of marketing include attracting customers in both local and external markets, enhancing product competitiveness, increasing sales volume and profitability, and continuously monitoring market trends. In market conditions, improving the efficiency and sustainability of enterprise development can primarily be achieved through the enhancement of marketing management. [2]. In this regard, relevant regulatory and legal documents have been adopted to regulate the marketing activities of regional trade enterprises. In particular, a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been adopted to ensure the legal regulation of retail trade conducted by legal entities and individuals within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan using a multi-level marketing system ("network marketing"). [3].

In addition, legal documents have been adopted to enhance the marketing effectiveness of enterprise activities. Specifically, a Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been adopted with the aim of further improving the efficiency of the activities of business entities and state unitary enterprises, reducing the level of state participation in the economy to a justified extent, and fundamentally improving the investment climate in the Republic of Uzbekistan. [4]. Effective regulation aimed at improving marketing efficiency is directly based on marketing activities. In other words, the mechanism for organizing, shaping, and regulating the strategic management of industrial enterprises on the basis of marketing is highly unique and represents a set of distinctive characteristics of the actions of economic entities. [5].

The regulation of the marketing activities of regional trade enterprises is carried out in a specific sequence and implemented on the basis of an algorithmic framework. That is, the algorithmic framework for regulating the marketing activities of regional trade enterprises consists of stages that ensure the systematic and sequential management of marketing processes, the standardization of decision-making, and the optimal use of resources. In this context, the algorithmic framework clearly defines the procedures for planning, implementing, and controlling marketing activities. As a result of applying the algorithmic framework, marketing decisions become systematic and effective, resources are used optimally, and costs are reduced; the competitiveness of products and services is enhanced; market share and profitability indicators increase steadily; and regional trade enterprises achieve sustainable development and strengthen their competitive positions.

The regulation of the marketing activities of regional trade enterprises also depends on the factors influencing them. As key factors of marketing strategy, the cyclical nature of reproduction processes and the elements of enterprise activity planning are examined [6]. Currently, in our country, the regulation of marketing activities of trade enterprises is being implemented through marketing research and promotional activities conducted via the regional sales network at Artel Electronics. At Uzbektelecom, marketing activities are regulated by adapting service packages to market demand, conducting online surveys, and measuring customer satisfaction. Based on these practices, the regulation of marketing activities of regional trade enterprises relies on the following elements and mechanisms (Table 1).

Table 1.
Regulation of the Marketing Activities of Regional Trade Enterprises ¹

No	Marketing Activity Element	Regulation Mechanism	Objective
1	Strategic Planning	Identifying market segments and forming the product portfolio	To develop the enterprise's long-term marketing strategy and allocate resources efficiently
2	Market Research	Studying various markets and analyzing customer needs	To determine demand and develop competitive pricing and advertising strategies
3	Product Policy	Developing and improving products and adapting them to target audiences	To enhance product competitiveness
4	Pricing Policy	Considering market competition and customer purchasing power	To optimize prices and increase profitability
5	Distribution and Logistics	Developing sales channels and the delivery system	To deliver products to end consumers and reduce costs
6	Advertising and Communication	Marketing campaigns, PR, and promotions	To attract customers and strengthen brand image
7	Innovative and Digital Marketing	E-commerce, online platforms, and mobile applications	To increase market share and attract new customers
8	Results Monitoring and Evaluation	KPIs, sales volume, and customer satisfaction	To assess and improve the effectiveness of marketing activities

Based on Table 1, the regulation of marketing activities for regional trade enterprises serves several key functions, including aligning products and services with market demand, enhancing competitiveness and profitability, monitoring market trends, identifying new opportunities, and establishing effective customer

¹ Compiled by the author

relationships. In this context, a marketing strategy refers to a set of actions developed on the basis of market conditions, competition, customer needs, and available resources, aimed at achieving the enterprise's long-term development goals. The primary significance of a marketing strategy for regional trade enterprises lies in its role in aligning products and services with market demand, strengthening competitive positions, increasing sales volume and profitability, as well as forecasting market trends and identifying new business opportunities.

In conclusion, the effective development and implementation of a marketing strategy for regional trade enterprises provides directions for designing products and services that meet market demand, enhancing competitiveness and profitability, strengthening customer relationships, developing new markets, optimizing resource allocation, and ensuring enterprise sustainability. As a result, the role of the marketing strategy ensures the long-term development and competitive position of regional trade enterprises.

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